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SATISFACTION LEVEL OF CONSUMERS IN REPLACEMENT TYRES IN COMMERCIAL VEHICLES

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Abstract

Consumer Satisfaction (CS) is a central concept in modern marketing thought and practice. The marketing concept emphasizes delivering satisfaction (not just products) to consumers and obtaining profits in return. As a result, overall quality of life is expected to be enhanced. Thus, consumer satisfaction is crucial to meeting various needs of consumers, business, and society. Satisfaction is a major outcome of marketing activity and serves to link processes culminating in purchase and consumption with post purchase phenomena such as attitude change, repeat purchase, and brand loyalty. This concept is not exempted in Replacement consumer also. The Indian Tyre industry derives its demand from the automobile industry. While OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturers) market off take is dependent on the new vehicle sales. Replacement market demand depends on the total population of vehicle on road, road conditions, vehicle scrapping rules, overloading norms for trucks, average life of tyres and prevalence of tyre retreading. This paper focused to study the satisfaction level of Commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres and various factors influencing their satisfaction level.

Keywords: Commercial Vehicles, Consumer Satisfaction, Replacement Tyres.

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer satisfaction is widely used in evaluating business performance both internally and externally. Internally, customer satisfaction is used to monitor performance, allocate resources, and compensate employees. Externally, customer satisfaction provides information to a wide range of interest group, including customers, competitors, and public policy makers. Consumer satisfaction judgments affect several postpurchase process of interest to researchers and managers. Complaining behaviour (Bearden and Teel 1983; Day 1984; Day and Landen 1977), Word-of-mouth communication (Richins 1983; Westbrook 1987), brand loyalty (Forenell 1976; Howard and Sheth 1969), and purchase intentions (Howard 1974; Labarbera and Mazursky 1983; Oliver 1980) have all been found

to be determinant at least in part by consumer satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

The tyre market is divided into two sectors: OE and replacement. OE tyres are defined as those supplied to vehicle makers to be fitted to new vehicles while replacement tyres are those which are fitted subsequently. Car and truck tyres are clearly the most widely used types of tyre, based on total value of sales. There is a wide range of both car and truck tyres designed to serve different purposes. Although brands have always played a part in tyre marketing, they have assumed much more importance in the last decade with the emergence of global players, and the acquisition of a portfolio of existing brands as a result of the takeover of other firms.

Table 1 : Automobile Production Trends (Number of Vehicles)

Category	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10
Passenger Vehicles	1309300	1545223	1777583	1838593	2351240
Commercial Vehicles	391083	519982	549006	416870	566608
Three Wheelers	434423	556126	500660	497020	619093
Two Wheelers	7608697	8466666	8026681	8419792	10512889
Grand Total	9743503	11087997	10853930	11172275	14049830

Source : SIAM

The increasing segmentation of the car market has led directly to a much more complex segmentation of the tyre market. Replacement market is one of the more sought-after markets by Tyre players, since the margins are better compared to those of OEM's (who are relatively few in number and have a huge bargaining power). Replacement demand, which comes from existing automobiles, has been increasing for sometime now and is expected to do the same, going forward. Replacement tyres varies across categories, due to different life-spans of tyres, which depends on reasons like, Road condition, Load carried, Distance traveled and Re-treading.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer satisfaction has been typically conceptualized as either an emotional (Cadotte, Woodruff, and Jenkins 1987; Westbrook and Reilly 1983) or cognitive response (Bolton and Drew 1991; Howard and Sheth 1969; Tse and Wilton 1988). For example, Westbrook and Reilly (1983) refer to satisfaction as "an emotional response," while Howard and Sheth (1969) refer to it as "a buyer's cognitive state."

The experiment shows that the overall tyre performance is based on five factors (in order of importance) appearance, durability, ride, traction, and handling (J.D. Power 2005) "tyre manufacturers not only need to provide better tyre performance but also need to focus on aligning strategies to customer expectations so they can provide a satisfactory tyre ownership experience".

J.D. Power (2008) study reveals that occurrence of problems, particularly during the initial ownership period, leads not only to increased dissatisfaction, but also to lower levels of customer loyalty and advocacy. Customers who report an initial quality problem are much less likely to repurchase or recommend the same make, compared with those who do not report experiencing a problem.

The study finds that the absence of tyre problems contributes to greater level of satisfaction and strongly influences customers perceptions of the tyre brand. Furthermore, problem-free tyre experience lead a higher degree of advocacy and loyalty for the tyre brand. Drivers of customer satisfaction and loyalty at the industry levels are expectation, image, product quality and service quality (Anne Martensen et. al. 2000) expectation have no or only a very limited impact on satisfaction and loyalty. Image is the main drivers for customer satisfaction. Service become a more important driver for bank customer loyalty. But image still has the largest impact on loyalty. The research has shown that satisfaction for a product is also related to how customers are satisfied by their buying experience (Pettijohn CE et al. 2002). The firms marketing success generally depends on the dealers, because these persons are the ones who have the most direct influence on the customers. In this sense, estimating customers judgment about their "buying experience" and evaluating the aspects that influence their perception of this service most, could help marketing the product a success.

Juan Delgado and Michael Waterson (2003) have found that almost all consumers buy tyres only when prompted by failure of the tyre by incident or at the annual road worthiness test, or as a result of their inspection that a tyre is worn out.

J.D. Power (2009) study shows that the occurrence of even a single problem leads to a strong negative impact on tyre satisfaction. Problems like excessive tyre noise while driving, poor traction on wet road and recurring flat tyres not only cause driving inconvenience, but also can be safety hazards, which intensifies the negative impact on customer satisfaction. This study also reveals that customer satisfaction with original equipment tyres has a strong impact on brand loyalty and advocacy for replacement tyres.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Consumer satisfaction is generally construed to be a postconsumption evaluation depends on perceived quality or value, expectation, and confirmation/disconfirmation. The study is aimed at to know the satisfaction level of replacement tyre consumers in Light and Heavy commercial vehicles, brand preference and factors influencing the customer satisfaction during their replacement decision.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To know the satisfaction level of Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres, quantitative research study was done as descriptive information was required over there. The researcher used survey method using schedules. The researcher personally involved in this research and collected primary data from the respondent. The respondents are - Owners of Bus, Trucks, and Light Commercial Vehicles. Data collection instruments were developed as a part of the study's total research design to systematize the collection of data

and to ensure that all the respondents are asked the same questions and in the same order. A Schedule was designed to know about the Purchase behaviour of Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres. Schedule designed includes both substantive questions that are relevant to Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners. The sampling plan addresses three questions: Whom to survey (the sampling unit), how many to survey (the sample size) and how to select them (the sampling procedure). The size of the sample is dependent both on the size of the budget and on the degree of confidence that the researcher wants to place in the findings. Here a sample size of 100 customers was selected using the Stratified Random Sampling technique. Appropriate statistical tools like descriptive and one way ANOVA were used to analyze the data collected.

5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

After all the customers were surveyed, i.e., a sample size of 100, the analysis was done on the basis of their responses in the following way:

Table 2 : Profile of the Respondents

	Factors	Frequency	Percent
Experience	Up to 5 years	11	11.0
	5- years	11	11.0
	10-15 years	13	13.0
	15- years	14	14.0
	20 years & above	51	51.0
Awareness through	Experience	98	98.0
	Friends	2	2.0
Awareness of Brands in years	Upto years	2	2.0
	Upto 5 years	9	9.0
	5-10 years	11	11.0
	10-15 years	13	13.0
	15-20 years	14	14.0
	20 years & above	51	51.0

Table 2 explains the experience, sources of awareness of the various brands of tyres and awareness of brands in years. Experience of respondent plays an important role in their purchasing behaviour of replacement tyres. Among the respondent of this study about 51 percent of respondents are having experience of more than 20 years. Among the respondents 98 percent of them are aware of the brands through experience and rest of the 2 percent of the respondent are aware of the brands through friends. (Pettijohn CE et al. 2002) has shown that satisfaction for a product is related to how customers are satisfied by their "buying experience". It shows that experience of a person place an important influencing factor to the

purchase of replacement tyres.

About 51 percent of the respondent having experience of 20 years and above and 14 percent of the respondent having experience of 15-20 years experience, and only 2 percent of the respondent having the experience of up to 2 years. (Gulorsen and Robert John 1994) examined the relative impact of four variables: product, information availability, experience and judgment ability. They were identified as having the major influence on consumer information. He also reported that experience, information availability, interaction of product type had a significant influence on the amount of search behaviour for goods.

Table 3 : Reason to Purchase a Select Brand

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
Reliability	2.8700	1.37551
Performance	3.1800	1.29006
Safety	2.5000	1.10554
Road Grip	2.8900	1.30960
Depth	3.0900	1.33405
Rolling Resistance	3.1500	1.21751
Delivery	3.0000	1.10096
Driver Recommendation	2.4000	1.68775
Quick Availability	2.6100	1.10000
Manufacturer Recommendation	2.1800	1.62294
Brand already fitted	3.2600	1.36048
Distributor Recommendation	2.3900	1.56924

Table 3 explains the reasons for purchasing selected brands by the respondent. Brands already fitted shows major reason for the purchase of the respondent followed by the performance of tyres, the manufacturer's recommendation and distributor recommendation is the least influencing factor for the purchase of replacement tyres. The study (J D Power 2009) reveals that customer satisfaction with original equipment tyres has a strong impact on brand loyalty and advocacy for replacement tyres. Customer who are highly satisfied are twice as likely to recommend

or repurchase their current tyre brand when buying replacement tyres. The owners those who are having 2-5 years of experience are highly favoured with Price, Reliability Performance, Road Grip, Depth, Rolling Resistance, Driver Recommendation, Quick availability of Tyres. And above 20 years experienced owners are influenced by Safety, Manufacturer Recommendation, and Distributor Recommendation for the purchase of Replacement Tyres. The New entrant is interested to purchase of Replacement tyre because of Speed of delivery and Brand already fitted.

Table 4 : Anova Table

Factors	Experience	Mean	Std. Deviation	F - Value	P - Value
Price	Up to 2 years	3.5000	.70711	1.027	.407 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	3.7778	.66667		
	5 – 10 Years	3.7273	.64667		
	10 – 15 Years	3.1538	.98710		
	15 – 20 Years	3.5000	.85485		
	20 Yrs & above	3.6667	.81650		
Reliability	Up to 2 years	2.0000	.00000	1.134	.348 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	3.3333	1.41421		
	5 – 10 Years	3.1818	1.60114		
	10 – 15 Years	3.0000	1.68325		
	15 – 20 Years	3.2857	1.54066		
	20 Yrs & above	3.6078	1.18454		
Performance	Up to 2 years	2.0000	.00000	.949	.454 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	3.5556	1.23603		
	5 – 10 Years	2.9091	1.30035		
	10 – 15 Years	3.3077	1.31559		
	15 – 20 Years	2.7857	1.18831		
	20 Yrs & above	3.2941	1.33108		
Safety	Up to 2 years	2.0000	.00000	.378	.863 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	2.2222	1.66667		
	5 – 10 Years	2.5455	1.43970		
	10 – 15 Years	2.4615	1.12660		
	15 – 20 Years	2.7857	1.18831		
	20 Yrs & above	3.2941	1.10223		
Road Grip	Up to 2 years	2.0000	.00000	.882	.496 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	3.5556	1.50923		
	5 – 10 Years	2.8182	1.40130		
	10 – 15 Years	2.9131	1.44115		
	15 – 20 Years	3.1429	1.23146		
	20 Yrs & above	2.7451	1.26243		
Depth	Up to 2 years	2.0000	.00000	2.009	.084 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	3.7778	1.39443		
	5 – 10 Years	2.8182	1.40130		
	10 – 15 Years	3.6154	1.38675		
	15 – 20 Years	3.5000	1.28602		
	20 Yrs & above	2.8235	1.26025		
Rolling Resistance	Up to 2 years	3.5000	2.12132	.767	.576 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	3.6667	1.32288		
	5 – 10 Years	2.9091	1.30035		
	10 – 15 Years	3.4615	1.26592		
	15 – 20 Years	3.2143	1.18831		
	20 Yrs & above	3.0000	1.16619		
Delivery	Up to 2 years	4.0000	.00000	.696	.628 (NS)
	2 – 5 Years	2.7778	.97183		
	5 – 10 Years	3.3636	.92442		
	10 – 15 Years	2.8462	1.14354		
	15 – 20 Years	3.0000	1.17670		
	20 Yrs & above	2.9608	1.14823		

Factors	Experience	Mean	Std. Deviation	F - Value	P - Value
Driver Recommendation	Up to 2 years	3.0000	2.82843	1.68	.146 (NS)
	2 - 5 Years	3.2222	1.92209		
	5 - 10 Years	2.1818	1.47093		
	10 - 15 Years	2.8462	1.72463		
	15 - 20 Years	1.4286	.85163		
	20 Yrs & above	2.4314	1.75790		
Quick Availability	Up to 2 years	2.0000	.00000	.953	.451 (NS)
	2 - 5 Years	3.2222	1.30171		
	5 - 10 Years	2.3636	.92442		
	10 - 15 Years	2.3846	.96077		
	15 - 20 Years	2.4000	.94054		
	20 Yrs & above	2.6667	1.17757		
Manufacturer Recommendation	Up to 2 years	1.0000	.00000	.770	.573 (NS)
	2 - 5 Years	2.2222	1.71594		
	5 - 10 Years	1.5455	1.29334		
	10 - 15 Years	2.5685	2.02548		
	15 - 20 Years	2.0000	1.66410		
	20 Yrs & above	2.3137	1.58101		
Brand already fitted	Up to 2 years	4.5000	.70711	.678	.641 (NS)
	2 - 5 Years	3.7778	1.39443		
	5 - 10 Years	3.0909	1.51357		
	10 - 15 Years	3.3077	1.49358		
	15 - 20 Years	3.1429	1.23146		
	20 Yrs & above	3.1765	1.35212		
Distributor Recommendation	Up to 2 years	1.0000	.00000	1.675	.148 (NS)
	2 - 5 Years	1.6667	1.00000		
	5 - 10 Years	1.7273	1.61808		
	10 - 15 Years	2.3077	1.47670		
	15 - 20 Years	2.3571	1.49908		
	20 Yrs & above	2.7451	1.64734		

Table 4 shows the ANOVA results based on the various factors which influence the consumer during their replacement action.

6. FINDINGS

From the study it is found that about 51 percent of the respondents having experience of more than 20 years. Experience of a person plays an important role of influencing factor for the purchase of replacement tyres. About 51 percent of the respondent know the brands for past 20 years and 14 percent of the respondents are heard the brand of 15-20 years, only 2 percent of the respondents are aware of the brand for 2 years. Brands already fitted shows major reason influencing the purchase behaviour of the respondent followed by the performance of

tyres. The variance analysis also explained that consumer satisfaction about the tyre Replacement (F-value of brand already fitted is 0.678 and F-value of performance of tyre is 0.949 and it is not significant. It shows that the consumer satisfied when they buy the already fitted brands, Manufacturers recommendation and distributors recommendation is the least influencing factor for the purchase of replacement tyres. Price factor mostly influences the respondent whose experience is between 2-5 years and the respondent state that the price of the tyre is moderately good, than the respondent whose experience is 10-15 years. Consumer consider Performance, Depth of tread, Rolling Resistance, Brand already fitted for select the purchase of particular brand of tyres.

7. CONCLUSION

The study conclude that there are different factors influencing the satisfaction level of owners in Heavy and Light Commercial Vehicles in replacement tyres. among the factors Brand already fitted with the vehicle plays an important factors in replacement of tyres and followed by the performance of tyres. And less experienced consumers are satisfied with Reliability of product, Performance, Road Grip, Depth, Rolling Resistance. Highly experienced consumer gives importance for safety.

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